

THE ID OF THE SUPERNUMERARY TOOTH

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EDUCATION

Abstract: *Teeth Numbering Systems help in easy communication and documentation of the tooth or teeth of concern. They are devised in a manner in which their implementation is easy. However, confusion arises when there is an additional tooth in the arch. This article explains how a supernumerary tooth is numbered.*

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There are 32 teeth in an adult and 20 in a child. A number can vary between them according to the age and the dental disease. But when you see an extra tooth in between, how will you put them into a notation?

The most widely used systems in dentistry are one of the following: Zsigmondy Palmer, FDI, and Universal Tooth Numbering System.^{1,2} But when we encounter a supernumerary tooth, we often fumble in denoting them.

There are multiple ways to denote a supernumerary tooth, but for starters, we shall stick to how to include them into the three basic systems. This gives specific information in regards to location, morphology and number of the supernumerary tooth to assist in easy communication in interdisciplinary dental care.

Figure 1 Supernumerary Tooth

Considering Fig 1 as an example, let us see how the supernumerary tooth is denoted in different notation systems

For Universal Tooth Numbering System

1 (S)

UNI-S

13

For FDI System

1 (S)

FDI-S

25

For Zsigmondy Palmer

The *superscript* would consist of two characters, a numerical character denoting the number of supernumeraries followed by alphabetical character (in bracket) showing their type(s). The type of supernumerary teeth is classified as, (conical = c, tuberculate = t, supplemental = s, and odontomas = o).

The *subscript* would denote the tooth number distal to which the supernumerary is located and if it is located in the midline, it would be denoted by “md” followed by abbreviation of upper or lower arch (md-u/md-l).

Abbreviation denoting the upper and lower arch will only be used in Universal and FDI systems as the arches are already represented by quadrants in Palmer system.⁴

The lack of understanding for location of a supernumerary can lead to a serious miscommunication between dentists regarding patient care. Therefore, an effective, easy to use and more explicit method should be used for clear communication and treatment plan.

REFERENCES

1. Ash M M, Stanley JN. (2005). Wheeler’s dental anatomy, physiology, and occlusion. 8th ed. Saunders Elsevier publication; 1-27.
2. American Dental Association. (2008). Council on Dental Practice: Dental Abbreviation, Symbols and Acronyms. Designation for teeth, 2nd ed. p. 35. Available from: <http://www.ada.org/sections/>
3. Andlaw RJ, Rock WP. (1996) A Manual of Paediatric Dentistry. 4th ed. New York: Churchill Livingstone; p. 156.
4. Mahmood A, Rizwan A, Nazir R. (2020). ‘MRN’ supernumerary notation for permanent dentition. POJ. 12(1) 9-17

